

MED024

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08/04/2021

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Last Version Update : mai 25, 2021

MEDICIS Collection

- ANSYS Simulation Report

Aim : Reproduce in ANSYS Thermal-Electric simulation workbench the Run 1 & Run 2 MED024 experiments performed at CERN MEDICIS.

ANSYS Version used : ANSYS 2019 R3

I. Introduction

At MEDICIS in CERN, **two collections of Ac-225** were made (MED024 experiment) : The objective of those collections of Ac-225 was to provide IKS, KU Leuven with a first batch of mass-separated Ac-225 for MED-024 “*Mass separation of ^{225}Ac from ^{227}Ac and from irradiated Th target to support Targeted Alpha Therapy.*”. In order to draw some conclusions on the Ac-225 release, we perform here a thermal simulation of the target unit at MEDICIS with and without a ThO_2 nugget. The idea is to understand why during the second run of the experiment, the experimentalist had to increase the target unit temperature, compared to run 1, to have a similar release of Actinium.

First collection, Run 1 : This collection was made between November 3 2020 and November 5 2020 at CERN MEDICIS. An Ac-225 solution had been placed inside a Ta sample boat with a rhenium foil (provided by CERN) and then evaporated.

Second collection, Run 2 : This collection was made between December 7 2020 and December 9 2020 at CERN MEDICIS. For this run, Ac-225 had been poured into a nugget of ThO_2 .

Figure 1: Picture of the run 2 boat unit with a rhenium foil and a ThO_2 nugget

To understand the temperature difference between the runs, **three sets of ANSYS Thermal-electric simulations** were made :

- One to understand the influence on the Temperature & Voltage of the boat position inside the target unit, which are named : **On Boat Positions**
- One to understand the influence on the Temperature of the ThO_2 nugget presence inside the target unit, which are named : **On Boat Positions with and without ThO_2 Nugget**
- One to understand the influence on the Temperature of the ThO_2 nugget size, but also see the difference between the Current/Time setting configuration between Run 1 & 2, which are named : **On ThO_2 Nugget Volumes**

II. Simulation Settings

1. Geometry

The target unit 3D-model is a simplified version of the MK1 Base used at ISOLDE/MEDICIS.

General Information:

- 16 Bodies (+ 1 with the ThO_2 Nugget)
- 15 Contact regions (+1 with the ThO_2 Nugget)

Boat Shape & Size

Boat	Size [mm]
Cylinder length	41.28
Cylinder inner diameter	16.25
Cylinder outer diameter	17.82
O-Ring inner diameter	12.83
O-Ring & End thickness	1

Foil Shape & Size

Figure 2: Foil 3D-Model with Boat shape in blue

Foil	Size [mm]
Foil thickness	0.025 (= 25 μm)
Foil length	36
Foil width	35.5

ThO₂ Nugget Shape & Size

Figure 3: Nugget 3D-Model with the Foil, Nugget in blue

Different volumes were tested for the nugget. The nugget length is the same for each volume, only the area of the nugget model change :

Nugget Model	Length [mm]	Area [mm^2]	Volume [mm^3]
Volume 1 (N1)	32	34.673	≈ 1104
Volume 2 (N2)	32	15.634	≈ 500
Volume 3 (N3)	32	3.284	≈ 105

2. Material & Meshing

Figure 4: 3D-Model with Body name

Figure 5: 3D-Model with Body name: Boat & Foil inside the target unit with a Zoom on Nugget

More details on Material parameters used are in Annex [B].

Body Name	Material	Mesh Element Size
ClampLine	Copper	5 mm
Clamp1	Copper	5 mm
Clamp2	Copper	5 mm
ClampBlock1	Copper	5 mm
ClampBlock2	Copper	5 mm
TargetTube	Tantalum	4 mm
TargetSide1	Tantalum	4 mm
TargetSide2	Tantalum	4 mm
ElectricConnect	Tantalum	4 mm
Plate	Tantalum	4 mm
TransferLine	Tantalum	2 mm
Support	Tantalum	2 mm
Boat	Tantalum	2 mm
Nugget	ThO₂	2 mm
Welding	Tantalum	0.5 mm
Ionizer	Rhenium	0.5 mm
Foil	Rhenium	0.5 mm

3. Load & Constraint

Figure 6: Load & Constraint position

Run 1

Constraint	Value	# Surface
Temperature	25 °C	6
Radiation-Ta (Option: Surface to Surface)	$\epsilon = 0.26$ & 25 °C	227
Radiation-Re (Option: Surface to Surface)	$\epsilon = 0.4$ & 25 °C	13
Voltage	0 V	2
Current-Line	290 A	1
Current-Target	600-720 A	1

Run 2

Constraint	Value	# Surface
Temperature	25 °C	6
Radiation-Ta (Option: Surface to Surface)	$\epsilon = 0.26$ & 25 °C	227
Radiation-Re (Option: Surface to Surface)	$\epsilon = 0.4$ & 25 °C	13
Voltage	0 V	2
Current-Line	290-305 A	1
Current-Target	50-810 A	1

Current load used for simulations

Configuration	Time	Current [A]	
		Line	Target
Run 1	0s	0	0
	8000s (2.22 hours)	290	600
	12000s (3.33 hours)	290	620
	19000s (5.28 hours)	290	640
	21500s (5.97 hours)	290	660
	28500s (7.92 hours)	290	680
	50000s (13.89 hours)	290	720
Run 2	0s	0	0
	8000s (2.22 hours)	290	50
	8960s (2.49 hours)	290	200
	11780s (3.27 hours)	290	400
	11960s (3.32 hours)	290	500
	13400s (3.72 hours)	290	550
	21200s (5.89 hours)	290	675
	26600s (7.39 hours)	290	700
	67510s (18.75 hours)	290	710
	69910s (19.42 hours)	290	730
	71710s (19.92 hours)	305	750
	84550s (23.49 hours)	305	780
	86410s (1 day)	305	790
	155000s (1.79 days)	305	810

4. Simulation General description

More details on ANSYS simulation settings used are in Annex [A].

Figure 7: Boat position & Current direction

Simulation without the Nugget: 4 boat positions made only with “Run 1” Current/Time configuration, with the 3D-model step file name used:

- **Position 0 (P0):** BaseMK1Sans-P0-V3.step
- **Position 1 (P1):** BaseMK1Sans-V12.step
- **Position 2 (P2):** BaseMK1Sans-CleanSurface-V5.step
- **Position 3 (P3):** BaseMK1Sans-V16.step

Simulation with the Nugget : 2 boat positions and 3 Nugget Volumes only for Position 2, made with “Run 1” & “Run 2” Current/Time configuration, with the 3D-model step file name used:

- **Position 1 (P1):** BaseMK1WithThO-P1-V3.step
- **Position 2 (P2):**
 - **Nugget Volume (N1):** BaseMK1WithThO-P2-V2.step
 - **Nugget Volume (N2):** BaseMK1WithThO-P2-V5.step
 - **Nugget Volume (N3):** BaseMK1WithThO-P2-V6.step

III. Summarized Results

To understand the temperature difference between the runs, **three sets of ANSYS Thermal-electric simulations** were made :

- One to understand the influence on the Temperature & Voltage of the boat position inside the target unit, which are named : **On Boat Positions**
- One to understand the influence on the Temperature of the ThO_2 nugget presence inside the target unit, which are named : **On Boat Positions with and without ThO_2 Nugget**
- One to understand the influence on the Temperature of the ThO_2 nugget size, but also see the difference between the Current/Time setting configuration between Run 1 & 2, which are named : **On ThO_2 Nugget Volumes**

- **Warning** : The ANSYS Thermal-Electric simulation workbench used to make those data is a **steady-state** simulation. That mean, the time inside those results are given in steady-state configuration. Those results will depends more on the current applied on the system and less on the time spend.
- **Warning** : The simulation on **Position 1 (P1) with a ThO_2 Nugget with Run 1 & Run 2** was **made with a small mistake** : the ANSYS contact region automatic generator create a wrong connection between the *Nugget* and the *Boat*, because the *Foil* in between the *Nugget* and the *Boat* are very small ($25 \mu\text{m}$). This wrong contact region was removed from all the simulations with a Nugget, but was forgotten for this simulation. **This might give a small error in the estimation of the Temperature of the *Nugget*, *Boat* and *Foil* for the simulation on Position 1 (P1) with a ThO_2 Nugget with Run 1 & Run 2.**
- **Warning** : those simulations are made with a **constant radiation emissivity** for rhenium (0.4) and tantalum (0.26). **The temperature might increase if we use radiation emissivity dependent on temperature**, but calculation time will increase too.
 - For tantalum a radiation emissivity of 0.26 correspond to a temperature between 2000-2100 °C.
 - For rhenium a radiation emissivity of 0.4 correspond to a temperature between 1600-1700 °C.

1. On Boat Positions

Simulations were made **without the ThO_2 nugget** where the boat is placed on **different positions** with **Run 1 the Current/Time configuration** :

- **Position 0** : placed on the left side of the Target unit
- **Position 1 & 2** : placed centered in the middle of the Target unit
- **Position 3** : placed on the right side of the Target unit
- **Result on Temperature**

Figure 8: Temperature profile with Boat at position P2

- The temperature range (min, max) of the whole system (**Total**) is more or less the same between the different positions, same when we select only the temperature range of the **Target**. We have a small shift between the position, but the same curve behavior. But we see a difference of average temperature as a function of the position when we look only at the tantalum **Boat** which includes **the boat and the foil**.
- The **highest average temperature** for the Boat is at the **position P2**, then **position P1** which are the two centered position inside the target unit. After we have **position P0** at lower current and then **position P3**. But this **order is reversed at higher current (> 660 A)** where **position P3** has a higher average temperature than **position P0**

- Those differences are made in absolute value.
- The maximum differences of average temperature between position on the whole system (**Total**) are **less than 70 °C** and only **less than 30 °C** for only the **Target**. The maximum differences are with the **position P0** : P0-P1, P0-P2, P0-P3. It's expected, as the **position P0** is one of the worst scenario where the boat slides to the left extreme part of the target unit.
- If we look only at the **boat average temperature difference**, we see bigger temperature differences. We have an average temperature differences superior to **> 60 °C** for position comparison between : **P0-P2, P0-P1, P2-P3, P1-P3**, it's when the "extreme" position are involved, so **position P0 & P3**. We have an average temperature differences inferior to **<40 °C** for position comparison between : P0-P3, P1-P2. For the difference between **P1-P2**, which are the smallest, it's expected as those two positions are close to each other in the target center. For the difference between **P0-P3**, this low difference in result might be understandable, because those positions are symmetrically placed on both sides of the target unit and then give the smallest temperature difference around ≈ 660 °C.

Figure 9: Boat temperature profile

- Result on Voltage

Figure 10: Target & Boat Voltage profile with Boat at position P2

- Again the average voltages between position on only the **Target** body are more or less the same, with a maximum average voltage for **position P3**.
- When we look at the average voltage on the whole system (**Total**), we see differences of around 0.1 V to 0.3 V between positions. Same when we are looking only on the boat average voltage, but even worse. The **higher average voltage on the boat** is obtained with the **position P3** with a voltage between around [1.8 V - 3 V]. Then after that we have **position P1 & P2** with a voltage between around [1 V - 1.25 V]. And finally the **position P0** with a voltage between around [0.5 V - 0.6 V]. Those results can be explained by direction of the current inside the target unit. **The current enters at the right side of the target unit and then flows along the target cylinder** and this current will be reduced as it advances inside the target unit. The current (and so the voltage) will be higher at **position P3** which is the position closer to the current “entrance”. Then it will go inside **position P1 & P2** and at last at **position P0**.

Figure 11: Target Voltage profil with the Boat at position P2

2. On Boat Positions with and without ThO_2 Nugget

Simulations were made **with & without the ThO_2 nugget** where the boat is placed at **two different positions** with **Run 1 the Current/Time configuration** :

- **Position 1 & 2** : placed centered in the middle of the Target unit

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Average Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

- We are getting more or less the same result **with & without the ThO_2 Nugget** at the different position.
- There is a small difference of average temperature on the **Target** body on **position P1 with & without the ThO_2 Nugget**. But it might be because a **mistake** which was made on the simulation configuration (more explanations in the beginning of the “Summarized Results” part).

Average Temperature Difference between With & Without a ThO Nugget Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Figure 12: Target Temperature with the Boat at position P1 With & Without a ThO_2 Nugget

3. On ThO_2 Nugget Volumes

Simulations were made **with the ThO_2 nugget at position P2 (middle of the target unit) with different nugget volumes** with **the Run 1 & Run 2 Current/Time configuration** :

- Nugget volume N1 = $\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$
- Nugget volume N2 = $\approx 500 \text{ mm}^3$
- Nugget volume N3 = $\approx 105 \text{ mm}^3$

Run 1

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm^3 , N2 = 500 mm^3 , N3 = 105 mm^3

- Changing the **Nugget volume** does not affect the whole system (**Total**) average temperature. It does not affect also the **Target** and the **Boat** body average temperature. Only the **Nugget** average temperature is affected by the change of volume. **The average nugget temperature is decreasing as the nugget volume is decreasing.**

Average Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

- Maximum temperature difference between **Nugget volume** is only around 3-4 °C, so very small.

Figure 13: Nugget Temperature with the Boat at position P2 for Run 1

Run 2

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

- We are getting the same result as the run 1 Current/Time configuration : Changing the Nugget volume does not affect the whole system (**Total**) average temperature. It does not affect also the **Target**, **Boat** and the **Nugget** body average temperature.

Average Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

- Maximum temperature difference between **Nugget volume** is around 5 °C at the higher current (800 A), so very small. But we can see that those differences of average temperature increase with the current, there will be lower at lower current and increase at higher current. This difference is of course bigger between the smaller and bigger volume **N1-N3**.

Figure 14: Nugget Temperature with the Boat at position P2 for Run 2

4. Conclusion

- The **Boat position** inside the target unit will mostly affect the **boat temperature** itself and less the whole system and the target. But the **Boat position** inside the target unit will affect drastically the **voltage inside the boat**. This effect is smaller when the boat is in the middle of the target unit (positions P1 & P2).
 - **Adding or removing a ThO_2 nugget** to the system **does not affect** the **temperature** or the **voltage** of the whole system or the boat itself. A small difference can be seen on the results, but might come from a wrong simulation configuration.
 - **Changing the volume size** of the nugget volume **does not affect** the **temperature** or the **voltage** of the **whole system or the boat itself**. But it changes a little bit the temperature of the nugget itself ($< 5^\circ\text{C}$).
-

IV. COMPLETE ANSYS RESULTS : On Boat Positions

1. Picture results

Position 0

- Temperature

- Voltage

Position 1

- Temperature

- Voltage

Position 2

- Temperature

- Voltage

Position 3

- Temperature

- Voltage

2. Graph results

Temperature range : $T[^\circ\text{C}]$ Vs $t[\text{s}]$

Position 2 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Position 3 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Temperature range : T[°C] Vs I[A]

Position P2 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Position P3 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Temperature range : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Target & Boat)

Position P0 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Position P1 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Position P2 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Position P3 : Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Temperature : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Position)

Target & Boat

Temperature : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Body)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Average Temperature

Maximum Temperature

Minimum Temperature

Temperature Difference between Position : T[°C] Vs I[A]

Minimum Temperature Difference

Voltage : U[V] Vs I[A] (Body)

Voltage range (min, max, avg)

Average Voltage

Voltage : U[V] Vs I[A] (Position)

Average Voltage range (Total)

Average Voltage (Total)

Average Voltage range (Target)

Average Voltage (Target)

3. Table results

Position 0

- P0 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.68	0.18	25	757.54	547.67
6,000	0	1.37	0.37	25	1,263.60	865.35
8,000	0	2.20	0.59	25	1,713.50	1,135.90
12,000	0	2.31	0.62	25	1,747.50	1,158.20
19,000	0	2.41	0.64	25	1,781.30	1,180.30
21,500	0	2.52	0.66	25	1,814.90	1,202.10
28,500	0	2.63	0.68	25	1,848.20	1,223.70
50,000	0	2.85	0.73	25	1,914.30	1,266.30

- P0 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	758	548	213	718	577	522	603	561
6,000	25	1,264	865	412	1,070	909	846	930	873
8,000	25	1,714	1,136	634	1,360	1,192	1,095	1,199	1,128
12,000	25	1,748	1,158	655	1,396	1,222	1,116	1,223	1,150
19,000	25	1,781	1,180	675	1,431	1,252	1,136	1,247	1,172
21,500	25	1,815	1,202	696	1,465	1,281	1,157	1,271	1,194
28,500	25	1,848	1,224	716	1,499	1,310	1,177	1,295	1,215
50,000	25	1,914	1,266	757	1,566	1,367	1,216	1,342	1,257

- P0 Table : Voltage

Time [s]	Voltage [V]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	-0.001	0.679	0.177	0.019	0.656	0.311	0.112	0.171	0.142
6,000	-0.001	1.372	0.367	0.037	1.327	0.630	0.235	0.355	0.296
8,000	-0.002	2.201	0.594	0.060	2.128	1.013	0.392	0.581	0.488
12,000	-0.002	2.305	0.616	0.062	2.228	1.056	0.407	0.603	0.507
19,000	-0.002	2.411	0.638	0.065	2.329	1.099	0.423	0.626	0.526
21,500	-0.002	2.518	0.660	0.067	2.432	1.144	0.439	0.648	0.546
28,500	-0.002	2.626	0.683	0.070	2.536	1.188	0.455	0.671	0.565
50,000	-0.002	2.848	0.729	0.075	2.748	1.279	0.487	0.718	0.605

Position 1

- P1 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.66	0.23	25	791.85	578.95
6,000	0	1.34	0.47	25	1,323.30	900.01
8,000	0	2.15	0.75	25	1,782.30	1,171.00
12,000	0	2.25	0.78	25	1,817.20	1,194.20
19,000	0	2.35	0.81	25	1,851.80	1,216.90
21,500	0	2.46	0.83	25	1,886.20	1,239.70
28,500	0	2.56	0.86	25	1,920.30	1,262.20
50,000	0	2.77	0.92	25	1,987.80	1,306.50

- P1 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	792	579	223	688	572	631	660	640
6,000	25	1,323	900	428	1,047	902	919	983	941
8,000	25	1,782	1,171	648	1,346	1,182	1,151	1,257	1,187
12,000	25	1,817	1,194	668	1,383	1,211	1,174	1,288	1,212
19,000	25	1,852	1,217	689	1,419	1,240	1,196	1,319	1,237
21,500	25	1,886	1,240	709	1,455	1,268	1,219	1,350	1,262
28,500	25	1,920	1,262	729	1,490	1,297	1,241	1,381	1,287
50,000	25	1,988	1,306	769	1,560	1,352	1,285	1,442	1,336

- P1 Table : Voltage

Time [s]	Voltage [V]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	-0.001	0.662	0.228	0.019	0.639	0.318	0.278	0.343	0.310
6,000	-0.001	1.341	0.469	0.036	1.297	0.645	0.568	0.694	0.631
8,000	-0.002	2.151	0.750	0.059	2.079	1.033	0.912	1.106	1.009
12,000	-0.002	2.251	0.778	0.061	2.174	1.075	0.946	1.149	1.047
19,000	-0.002	2.352	0.805	0.063	2.271	1.118	0.980	1.191	1.085
21,500	-0.002	2.455	0.833	0.066	2.369	1.162	1.015	1.235	1.124
28,500	-0.002	2.559	0.861	0.068	2.469	1.206	1.050	1.278	1.164
50,000	-0.002	2.772	0.918	0.073	2.672	1.295	1.122	1.368	1.243

Position 2

- P2 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.65	0.25	25	819.08	589.75
6,000	0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.32
8,000	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,822.00	1,189.50
12,000	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.50	1,213.60
19,000	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.10
28,500	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.10	1,330.80

- P2 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	819	590	221	664	565	635	651	642
6,000	25	1,360	915	421	1,015	892	931	976	948
8,000	25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,170	1,253	1,200
12,000	25	1,858	1,214	655	1,364	1,199	1,196	1,286	1,228
19,000	25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,223	1,318	1,256
21,500	25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,249	1,351	1,284
28,500	25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,274	1,383	1,311
50,000	25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,325	1,447	1,365

- P2 Table : Voltage

Time [s]	Voltage [V]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	-0.001	0.650	0.252	0.019	0.627	0.317	0.278	0.343	0.310
6,000	-0.001	1.314	0.512	0.036	1.270	0.640	0.568	0.694	0.631
8,000	-0.002	2.107	0.816	0.057	2.034	1.022	0.912	1.106	1.009
12,000	-0.002	2.203	0.846	0.059	2.126	1.063	0.946	1.149	1.047
19,000	-0.002	2.300	0.876	0.062	2.220	1.105	0.980	1.191	1.085
21,500	-0.002	2.400	0.907	0.064	2.315	1.147	1.015	1.235	1.124
28,500	-0.002	2.501	0.938	0.066	2.411	1.190	1.050	1.278	1.164
50,000	-0.002	2.706	1.000	0.071	2.607	1.277	1.122	1.368	1.243

Position 3

- P3 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.66	0.31	25	837.45	556.56
6,000	0	1.33	0.63	25	1,379.60	887.17
8,000	0	2.12	1.00	25	1,842.50	1,169.80
12,000	0	2.21	1.04	25	1,878.30	1,195.70
19,000	0	2.31	1.08	25	1,913.90	1,221.30
21,500	0	2.41	1.12	25	1,949.20	1,246.60
28,500	0	2.51	1.16	25	1,984.30	1,271.60
50,000	0	2.71	1.25	25	2,053.50	1,321.00

- P3 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	837	557	230	701	575	380	571	482
6,000	25	1,380	887	437	1,050	903	660	928	806
8,000	25	1,842	1,170	654	1,344	1,181	928	1,231	1,089
12,000	25	1,878	1,196	680	1,379	1,210	961	1,268	1,123
19,000	25	1,914	1,221	700	1,414	1,238	995	1,304	1,157
21,500	25	1,949	1,247	721	1,449	1,267	1,029	1,340	1,190
28,500	25	1,984	1,272	741	1,484	1,295	1,062	1,375	1,223
50,000	25	2,054	1,321	782	1,554	1,350	1,128	1,444	1,288

- P3 Table : Voltage

Time [s]	Voltage [V]								
	Total			Target			Boat & Foil		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	-0.001	0.663	0.312	0.019	0.641	0.340	0.559	0.618	0.591
6,000	-0.001	1.327	0.630	0.035	1.286	0.683	1.117	1.239	1.183
8,000	-0.002	2.116	1.002	0.057	2.049	1.089	1.772	1.971	1.879
12,000	-0.002	2.211	1.041	0.059	2.140	1.133	1.848	2.058	1.961
19,000	-0.002	2.308	1.081	0.061	2.233	1.178	1.925	2.146	2.044
21,500	-0.002	2.407	1.121	0.063	2.328	1.224	2.003	2.236	2.129
28,500	-0.002	2.507	1.162	0.066	2.424	1.270	2.083	2.327	2.214
50,000	-0.003	2.712	1.245	0.070	2.620	1.365	2.245	2.513	2.389

V. COMPLETE ANSYS RESULTS : On Boat Positions with and without ThO_2 Nugget

1. Picture results

Position P1 with ThO_2 Nugget, Run 1

Position P1 with ThO_2 Nugget, Run 2

Position P2 with ThO_2 Nugget, Run 1

Position P2 with ThO_2 Nugget, Run 2

2. Graph results

Temperature range : $T[^\circ\text{C}]$ Vs $t[\text{h}]$ (With & Without Nugget)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature range : T[°C] Vs I[A] (With & Without Nugget)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature : T[°C] Vs I[A] (With & Without Nugget)

Average Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Maximum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Minimum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature Zoom on Body : T[°C] Vs I[A] (With & Without Nugget)

Average Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Maximum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Minimum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Average Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Maximum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Minimum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Average Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Maximum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Minimum Temperature

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Temperature Difference : T[°C] Vs I[A] (With & Without Nugget)

Average Temperature Difference between With & Without a ThO Nugget

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Maximum Temperature Difference between With & Without a ThO Nugget

Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Minimum Temperature Difference between With & Without a ThO Nugget Nugget Volume N1 ($\approx 1104 \text{ mm}^3$)

Voltage : U[V] Vs I[A] (With & Without Nugget)

Average Voltage range (Total)

Average Voltage (Total)

3. Table results

Position 1, Without Nugget

- P1-Without Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.66	0.23	25	791.85	578.95
6,000	0	1.34	0.47	25	1,323.30	900.01
8,000	0	2.15	0.75	25	1,782.30	1,171.00
12,000	0	2.25	0.78	25	1,817.20	1,194.20
19,000	0	2.35	0.81	25	1,851.80	1,216.90
21,500	0	2.46	0.83	25	1,886.20	1,239.70
28,500	0	2.56	0.86	25	1,920.30	1,262.20
50,000	0	2.77	0.92	25	1,987.80	1,306.50

- P1-Without Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	792	579	223	688	572	631	660	640
6,000	25	1,323	900	428	1,047	902	919	983	941
8,000	25	1,782	1,171	648	1,346	1,182	1,151	1,257	1,187
12,000	25	1,817	1,194	668	1,383	1,211	1,174	1,288	1,212
19,000	25	1,852	1,217	689	1,419	1,240	1,196	1,319	1,237
21,500	25	1,886	1,240	709	1,455	1,268	1,219	1,350	1,262
28,500	25	1,920	1,262	729	1,490	1,297	1,241	1,381	1,287
50,000	25	1,988	1,306	769	1,560	1,352	1,285	1,442	1,336

Position 1, With Nugget

- P1-With Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.66	0.23	25	791.44	579.92
6,000	0	1.35	0.47	25	1,322.30	900.50
8,000	0	2.16	0.75	25	1,780.90	1,171.00
12,000	0	2.26	0.78	25	1,815.80	1,194.10
19,000	0	2.36	0.81	25	1,850.40	1,217.10
21,500	0	2.46	0.84	25	1,884.80	1,239.80
28,500	0	2.57	0.86	25	1,919.00	1,262.30
50,000	0	2.78	0.92	25	1,986.40	1,306.70

- P1-With Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	791	580	223	691	574	633	661	641
6,000	25	1,322	900	428	1,052	905	921	983	941
8,000	25	1,781	1,171	647	1,352	1,185	1,152	1,256	1,187
12,000	25	1,816	1,194	668	1,389	1,215	1,176	1,287	1,213
19,000	25	1,850	1,217	688	1,425	1,244	1,198	1,318	1,238
21,500	25	1,885	1,240	708	1,460	1,272	1,221	1,349	1,263
28,500	25	1,919	1,262	728	1,496	1,300	1,244	1,380	1,287
50,000	25	1,986	1,307	768	1,565	1,356	1,288	1,440	1,336

Position 2, Without Nugget

- P2-Without Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.65	0.25	25	819.08	589.75
6,000	0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.32
8,000	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,822.00	1,189.50
12,000	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.50	1,213.60
19,000	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.10
28,500	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.10	1,330.80

- P2-Without Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	819	590	221	664	565	635	651	642
6,000	25	1,360	915	421	1,015	892	931	976	948
8,000	25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,170	1,253	1,200
12,000	25	1,858	1,214	655	1,364	1,199	1,196	1,286	1,228
19,000	25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,223	1,318	1,256
21,500	25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,249	1,351	1,284
28,500	25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,274	1,383	1,311
50,000	25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,325	1,447	1,365

Position 2, With Nugget

- P2-With Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	0	0.65	0.25	25	819.09	590.13
6,000	0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.51
8,000	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,822.00	1,189.50
12,000	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.50	1,213.70
19,000	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.20
28,500	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.10	1,331.00

- P2-With Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Temperature [°C]								
	min	Total		Target			Boat & Foil		
		max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	25	819	590	221	664	565	636	651	642
6,000	25	1,360	916	421	1,015	892	932	975	948
8,000	25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,171	1,252	1,200
12,000	25	1,858	1,214	655	1,364	1,199	1,198	1,286	1,229
19,000	25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,224	1,318	1,256
21,500	25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,250	1,351	1,284
28,500	25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,276	1,383	1,311
50,000	25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,326	1,447	1,366

VI. COMPLETE ANSYS RESULTS : On ThO_2 Nugget Volumes

1. Picture results

Nugget Volume N1, Run 1 (Position P2)

Nugget Volume N1, Run 2 (Position P2)

Nugget Volume N2, Run 1 (Position P2)

Nugget Volume N2, Run 2 (Position P2)

Nugget Volume N3, Run 1 (Position P2)

Nugget Volume N3, Run 2 (Position P2)

2. Graph results

Temperature range, Run 1 : T[°C] Vs t[h] (Nugget Volume Size)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range, Run 1 : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Nugget Volume Size)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature, Run 1 : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Nugget Volume Size)

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature Difference between Position, Run 1 : T[°C] Vs I[A]

Average Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Voltage, Run 1 : U[V] Vs I[A]

Average Voltage range (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 1, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range, Run 2 : T[°C] Vs t[h] (Nugget Volume Size)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range, Run 2 : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Nugget Volume Size)

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature range (min, max, avg)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature, Run 2 : T[°C] Vs I[A] (Nugget Volume Size)

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Temperature Difference between Position, Run 2 : T[°C] Vs I[A]

Average Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Temperature Difference

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Voltage, Run 2 : U[V] Vs I[A]

Average Voltage range (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Average Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Maximum Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

Minimum Voltage (Total)

Time/Current Configuration : Run 2, Nugget Volume : N1 = 1104 mm³, N2 = 500 mm³, N3 = 105 mm³

3. Table results

Position 2, Nugget Volume N1

- P2-N1 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Configuration	Current [A]		Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
		Line	Target	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
0	Run 1	0	0						
4,000				0	0.65	0.25	25	819.09	590.13
6,000				0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.51
8,000		290	600	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,822.00	1,189.50
12,000		290	620	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.50	1,213.70
19,000		290	640	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500		290	660	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.20
28,500		290	680	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000		290	720	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.10	1,331.00
0		Run 2	0	0					
4,000				0	0.17	0.04	25	245.85	159.91
4,800				0	0.24	0.06	25	358.55	220.51
5,600				0	0.32	0.07	25	482.17	284.04
6,400				0	0.41	0.10	25	606.12	348.74
7,200				0	0.52	0.12	25	724.50	411.57
8,000	290		50	0	0.63	0.15	25	834.95	471.46
8,960	290		200	0	0.81	0.29	25	1,014.60	654.06
11,780	290		400	0	1.23	0.53	25	1,438.90	932.71
11,960	290		500	0	1.65	0.67	25	1,639.70	1,065.10
13,400	290		550	0	1.87	0.75	25	1,732.00	1,128.20
21,200	290		675	0	2.48	0.93	25	1,953.80	1,278.80
26,600	290		700	0	2.60	0.97	25	1,996.90	1,307.90
67,510	290		710	0	2.65	0.99	25	2,014.00	1,319.40
69,910	290		730	0	2.76	1.02	25	2,048.10	1,342.40
71,710	305		750	0	2.89	1.07	25	2,111.70	1,378.50
84,550	305		780	0	3.05	1.12	25	2,161.30	1,412.10
86,410	305		790	0	3.11	1.14	25	2,177.70	1,423.10
155,000	305		810	0	3.22	1.17	25	2,210.10	1,445.20

• *P2-N1 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Configuration	Temperature [°C]											
		Total			Target			Boat & Foil			Nugget		
		min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	Run 1	25	819	590	221	664	565	636	651	642	636	645	639
6,000		25	1,360	916	421	1,015	892	932	975	948	932	959	940
8,000		25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,171	1,252	1,200	1,172	1,221	1,186
12,000		25	1,858	1,214	655	1,364	1,199	1,198	1,286	1,229	1,198	1,252	1,213
19,000		25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,224	1,318	1,256	1,225	1,282	1,240
21,500		25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,250	1,351	1,284	1,251	1,312	1,267
28,500		25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,276	1,383	1,311	1,276	1,342	1,293
50,000		25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,326	1,447	1,366	1,327	1,400	1,346
4,000		Run 2	25	246	160	40	181	107	117	139	128	120	136
4,800	25		359	221	47	255	145	159	192	176	164	188	176
5,600	25		482	284	54	334	187	203	249	225	210	242	226
6,400	25		606	349	62	415	231	247	307	276	256	298	276
7,200	25		724	412	69	493	277	290	364	325	300	353	326
8,000	25		835	471	76	567	321	329	418	372	341	405	372
8,960	25		1,015	654	158	713	524	530	619	569	538	602	567
11,780	25		1,439	933	412	996	859	883	934	900	883	917	892
11,960	25		1,640	1,065	535	1,134	1,020	1,033	1,084	1,055	1,034	1,065	1,044
13,400	25		1,732	1,128	585	1,229	1,096	1,103	1,169	1,129	1,104	1,144	1,116
21,200	25		1,954	1,279	709	1,466	1,276	1,269	1,375	1,305	1,270	1,334	1,287
26,600	25		1,997	1,308	733	1,511	1,310	1,301	1,415	1,339	1,302	1,371	1,320
67,510	25		2,014	1,319	743	1,529	1,324	1,313	1,431	1,352	1,314	1,386	1,332
69,910	25		2,048	1,342	763	1,565	1,351	1,339	1,462	1,379	1,340	1,415	1,358
71,710	25		2,112	1,378	794	1,601	1,385	1,367	1,496	1,409	1,368	1,446	1,388
84,550	25		2,161	1,412	823	1,653	1,425	1,403	1,542	1,448	1,405	1,488	1,426
86,410	25		2,178	1,423	833	1,670	1,438	1,415	1,557	1,461	1,417	1,502	1,438
155,000	25		2,210	1,445	853	1,704	1,464	1,439	1,588	1,487	1,441	1,530	1,463

Position 2, Nugget Volume N2

- *P2-N2 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Configuration	Current [A]		Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
		Line	Target	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
0	Run 1	0	0						
4,000				0	0.65	0.25	25	820.98	593.91
6,000				0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.44
8,000		290	600	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,821.90	1,189.50
12,000		290	620	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.40	1,213.60
19,000		290	640	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500		290	660	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.10
28,500		290	680	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000		290	720	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.00	1,330.90
0	Run 2	0	0						
2,000				0	0.06	0.02	25	67.00	51.17
4,000				0	0.17	0.04	25	245.92	160.03
4,800				0	0.24	0.06	25	358.63	220.67
5,600				0	0.32	0.07	25	482.25	284.24
6,400				0	0.41	0.10	25	606.15	348.89
7,200				0	0.52	0.12	25	724.54	411.82
8,000		290	50	0	0.63	0.15	25	834.96	471.74
8,960		290	200	0	0.81	0.29	25	1,014.60	654.26
11,780		290	400	0	1.23	0.53	25	1,438.80	932.82
11,960		290	500	0	1.65	0.67	25	1,639.70	1,065.20
13,400		290	550	0	1.87	0.74	25	1,732.00	1,128.30
21,200		290	675	0	2.48	0.93	25	1,953.80	1,278.80
26,600		290	700	0	2.60	0.97	25	1,996.90	1,307.90
67,510		290	710	0	2.65	0.99	25	2,014.00	1,319.30
69,910		290	730	0	2.76	1.02	25	2,048.00	1,342.40
71,710		305	750	0	2.89	1.07	25	2,111.70	1,378.50
84,550		305	780	0	3.05	1.12	25	2,161.30	1,412.00
86,410		305	790	0	3.11	1.13	25	2,177.70	1,423.10
155,000		305	810	0	3.22	1.17	25	2,210.00	1,445.20

• P2-N2 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Configuration	Temperature [°C]											
		Total			Target			Boat & Foil			Nugget		
		min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	Run 1	25	821	594	222	669	569	645	658	651	645	653	648
6,000		25	1,360	915	421	1,015	892	932	976	948	932	958	939
8,000		25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,170	1,253	1,200	1,171	1,218	1,184
12,000		25	1,857	1,214	654	1,364	1,199	1,197	1,286	1,228	1,198	1,248	1,211
19,000		25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,223	1,318	1,256	1,224	1,278	1,238
21,500		25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,249	1,351	1,284	1,250	1,308	1,265
28,500		25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,275	1,383	1,311	1,276	1,338	1,291
50,000		25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,326	1,447	1,366	1,327	1,396	1,343
2,000		Run 2	25	67	51	27	54	40	41	46	44	42	45
4,000	25		246	160	40	181	107	117	139	128	120	136	128
4,800	25		359	221	47	256	145	159	193	176	164	188	176
5,600	25		482	284	54	335	187	203	249	225	209	243	226
6,400	25		606	349	62	415	231	247	307	276	255	299	276
7,200	25		725	412	69	493	277	289	365	325	299	354	325
8,000	25		835	472	76	567	321	329	419	372	340	406	371
8,960	25		1,015	654	158	713	524	529	619	569	538	603	566
11,780	25		1,439	933	413	996	859	883	934	900	883	915	892
11,960	25		1,640	1,065	535	1,134	1,020	1,033	1,084	1,055	1,033	1,062	1,043
13,400	25		1,732	1,128	585	1,229	1,096	1,103	1,169	1,129	1,104	1,141	1,115
21,200	25		1,954	1,279	709	1,466	1,276	1,269	1,375	1,305	1,270	1,330	1,285
26,600	25		1,997	1,308	733	1,511	1,310	1,300	1,415	1,339	1,301	1,367	1,318
67,510	25		2,014	1,319	743	1,529	1,324	1,313	1,431	1,352	1,314	1,381	1,330
69,910	25		2,048	1,342	763	1,565	1,351	1,338	1,463	1,379	1,339	1,410	1,356
71,710	25		2,112	1,378	794	1,601	1,385	1,366	1,496	1,409	1,367	1,441	1,385
84,550	25		2,161	1,412	823	1,653	1,425	1,403	1,542	1,448	1,404	1,483	1,423
86,410	25		2,178	1,423	833	1,670	1,438	1,415	1,557	1,461	1,416	1,496	1,435
155,000	25		2,210	1,445	852	1,704	1,464	1,439	1,588	1,487	1,440	1,524	1,460

Position 2, Nugget Volume N3

• P2-N3 Table : Voltage & Temperature (Total)

Time [s]	Configuration	Current [A]		Voltage [V]			Temperature [°C]		
		Line	Target	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
0	Run 1	0	0						
4,000				0	0.65	0.25	25	819.08	589.85
6,000				0	1.31	0.51	25	1,359.50	915.42
8,000		290	600	0	2.11	0.82	25	1,821.90	1,189.50
12,000		290	620	0	2.20	0.85	25	1,857.50	1,213.60
19,000		290	640	0	2.30	0.88	25	1,892.70	1,237.50
21,500		290	660	0	2.40	0.91	25	1,927.70	1,261.10
28,500		290	680	0	2.50	0.94	25	1,962.40	1,284.60
50,000		290	720	0	2.71	1.00	25	2,031.10	1,330.90
0		Run 2	0	0					
2,000				0	0.06	0.02	25	67.02	51.20
4,000				0	0.17	0.04	25	245.98	160.13
4,800				0	0.24	0.06	25	358.67	220.78
5,600				0	0.32	0.07	25	482.31	284.40
6,400				0	0.41	0.10	25	606.24	349.15
7,200				0	0.52	0.12	25	724.51	411.96
8,000	290		50	0	0.63	0.15	25	834.97	471.99
8,960	290		200	0	0.81	0.29	25	1,014.60	654.34
11,780	290		400	0	1.23	0.53	25	1,438.80	932.90
11,960	290		500	0	1.65	0.67	25	1,639.70	1,065.30
13,400	290		550	0	1.87	0.74	25	1,732.00	1,128.30
21,200	290		675	0	2.48	0.93	25	1,953.80	1,278.80
26,600	290		700	0	2.60	0.97	25	1,996.90	1,307.70
67,510	290		710	0	2.65	0.99	25	2,014.00	1,319.40
69,910	290		730	0	2.76	1.02	25	2,048.10	1,342.30
71,710	305		750	0	2.89	1.07	25	2,111.70	1,378.40
84,550	305		780	0	3.05	1.12	25	2,161.30	1,412.00
86,410	305		790	0	3.11	1.13	25	2,177.70	1,423.00
155,000	305		810	0	3.22	1.17	25	2,210.10	1,445.10

• P2-N3 Table : Temperature

Time [s]	Configuration	Temperature [°C]											
		Total			Target			Boat & Foil			Nugget		
		min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
4,000	Run 1	25	819	590	221	664	565	635	651	642	635	644	638
6,000		25	1,360	915	421	1,015	892	932	976	948	932	956	939
8,000		25	1,822	1,190	635	1,326	1,170	1,170	1,253	1,200	1,171	1,214	1,183
12,000		25	1,858	1,214	655	1,364	1,199	1,197	1,286	1,228	1,198	1,245	1,210
19,000		25	1,893	1,238	674	1,401	1,227	1,223	1,318	1,256	1,224	1,274	1,237
21,500		25	1,928	1,261	694	1,438	1,255	1,249	1,351	1,284	1,250	1,304	1,263
28,500		25	1,962	1,285	714	1,475	1,283	1,275	1,383	1,311	1,276	1,333	1,290
50,000		25	2,031	1,331	753	1,547	1,338	1,325	1,447	1,366	1,326	1,390	1,342
2,000		Run 2	25	67	51	27	54	40	41	46	44	42	45
4,000	25		246	160	40	181	107	116	140	128	120	136	128
4,800	25		359	221	47	256	145	158	193	175	163	188	176
5,600	25		482	284	54	335	187	202	250	225	209	242	225
6,400	25		606	349	62	416	231	246	308	276	254	299	276
7,200	25		725	412	69	494	277	288	365	325	298	353	325
8,000	25		835	472	76	567	321	328	420	372	340	405	371
8,960	25		1,015	654	158	713	524	528	619	568	537	602	566
11,780	25		1,439	933	413	996	859	882	935	900	882	914	891
11,960	25		1,640	1,065	535	1,134	1,020	1,032	1,085	1,055	1,033	1,060	1,042
13,400	25		1,732	1,128	585	1,229	1,096	1,102	1,169	1,129	1,103	1,138	1,114
21,200	25		1,954	1,279	709	1,466	1,276	1,268	1,375	1,305	1,269	1,326	1,283
26,600	25		1,997	1,308	733	1,511	1,310	1,300	1,415	1,338	1,301	1,362	1,316
67,510	25		2,014	1,319	743	1,529	1,324	1,313	1,431	1,352	1,314	1,376	1,329
69,910	25		2,048	1,342	763	1,565	1,351	1,338	1,463	1,379	1,339	1,404	1,354
71,710	25		2,112	1,378	794	1,601	1,385	1,366	1,496	1,409	1,367	1,435	1,383
84,550	25		2,161	1,412	824	1,653	1,425	1,402	1,542	1,448	1,404	1,476	1,421
86,410	25		2,178	1,423	833	1,670	1,438	1,414	1,558	1,461	1,416	1,490	1,433
155,000	25		2,210	1,445	853	1,704	1,464	1,438	1,588	1,487	1,440	1,517	1,458

Annex

[A] ANSYS Simulations : Analysis Settings

General settings :

Step Controls	Run 1	Run 2
Number of steps	6	13
Current Step Numbers	6	13
Step End Time	50 000 s	1.55×10^5 s
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled	Program Controlled

Solver Controls	Run 1 & 2
Solver Type	Program Controlled

Radiosity Controls	Run 1 & 2
Radiosity solver	Program Controlled
Flux Convergence	1×10^{-4}
Maximum iteration	10 000
Solver Tolerance	0.1 W/m^2
Over Relaxation	0.1
Hemicube resolution	10

Nonlinear Controls	Run 1 & 2
Heat Convergence	Program Controlled
Temperature Convergence	Program Controlled
Line Search	On
Voltage Convergence	Program Controlled
Current Convergence	Program Controlled

[B] Material Parameters

Copper

- **Density** : 8900 kgm^{-3}
- **Coefficient of Thermal Expansion** : $1.65 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
- **Thermal Conductivity** : $400 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
- **Specific Heat** : $1 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Jkg}^{-1}\text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ at $26.85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
- **Resisitivity** :

Temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]	Resistivity [Ωm]
-272.15	2×10^{-11}
-269.15	2×10^{-11}
-266.15	2×10^{-11}
-263.15	2.02×10^{-11}
-258.15	2.18×10^{-11}
-253.15	2.8×10^{-11}
-248.15	4.49×10^{-11}
-243.15	8.28×10^{-11}
-238.15	1.47×10^{-10}
-233.15	2.39×10^{-10}
-228.15	3.58×10^{-10}
-223.15	5.18×10^{-10}
-218.15	7.27×10^{-10}
-213.15	9.71×10^{-10}
-203.15	1.54×10^{-9}
-193.15	2.15×10^{-9}
-183.15	2.81×10^{-9}
-173.15	3.48×10^{-9}
-148.15	5.22×10^{-9}
-123.15	6.99×10^{-9}
-98.15	8.74×10^{-9}
-73.15	1.046×10^{-8}
-48.15	1.217×10^{-8}
-23.15	1.387×10^{-8}
0	1.543×10^{-8}
19.85	1.678×10^{-8}
26.85	1.725×10^{-8}

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
76.85	2.063×10^{-8}
126.85	2.402×10^{-8}
226.85	3.09×10^{-8}
326.85	3.792×10^{-8}
426.85	4.514×10^{-8}
526.85	5.262×10^{-8}
626.85	6.041×10^{-8}
726.85	6.858×10^{-8}
826.85	7.717×10^{-8}
926.85	8.626×10^{-8}
1026.85	9.592×10^{-8}
1084.45	1.0171×10^{-7}

Tantalum

- Density : 16 650 kgm^{-3}
- Thermal Conductivity :

Temperature [°C]	Thermal Conductivity [$Wm^{-1}C^{-1}$]
0.05	57.4
25.05	57.5
26.85	57.5
50.05	57.6
76.85	57.6
100.05	57.7
126.85	57.8
200.05	58.2
226.85	58.2
300.05	58.5
326.85	58.6
400.05	58.8
426.85	59
500.05	59.3
526.85	59.4
600.05	59.7
626.85	59.8
700.05	60.2
726.85	60.2
800.05	60.5
826.85	60.6
900.05	60.9
926.85	61
1000.05	61.3
1026.85	61.4
1100.05	61.7
1126.85	61.8
1200.05	62.2
1226.85	62.2
1300.05	62.5
1326.85	62.6
1400.05	62.9

Temperature [°C]	Thermal Conductivity [$Wm^{-1}C^{-1}$]
1426.85	63
1500.05	63.3
1526.85	63.4
1600.05	63.7
1626.85	63.8
1700.05	64
1726.85	64.1
1800.05	64.4
1900.05	64.7
1926.85	64.8
2000.05	65
2126.85	65.4
2200.05	65.6
2326.85	65.9
2400.05	66.1
2526.85	66.4
2600.05	66.5
2726.85	66.6
2799.85	66.6
2926.85	66.6

• **Resistivity :**

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
-269.15	1×10^{-9}
-266.15	1.004×10^{-9}
-263.15	1.022×10^{-9}
-258.15	1.113×10^{-9}
-253.15	1.463×10^{-9}
-248.15	2.24×10^{-9}
-243.15	3.62×10^{-9}
-238.15	5.48×10^{-9}
-233.15	7.5×10^{-9}
-228.15	9.61×10^{-9}
-223.15	1.184×10^{-8}

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
-213.15	1.645×10^{-8}
-203.15	2.127×10^{-8}
-193.15	2.62×10^{-8}
-183.15	3.123×10^{-8}
-173.15	3.638×10^{-8}
-123.15	6.188×10^{-8}
-73.15	8.655×10^{-8}
-23.15	1.109×10^{-7}
-0.15	1.22×10^{-7}
19.85	1.315×10^{-7}
26.85	1.348×10^{-7}
76.85	1.582×10^{-7}
126.85	1.822×10^{-7}
176.85	2.061×10^{-7}
226.85	2.295×10^{-7}
276.85	2.522×10^{-7}
326.85	2.745×10^{-7}
376.85	2.968×10^{-7}
426.85	3.188×10^{-7}
476.85	3.399×10^{-7}
526.85	3.604×10^{-7}
576.85	3.814×10^{-7}
626.85	4.026×10^{-7}
676.85	4.228×10^{-7}
726.85	4.424×10^{-7}
826.85	4.815×10^{-7}
926.85	5.193×10^{-7}
1026.85	5.561×10^{-7}
1126.85	5.923×10^{-7}
1226.85	6.275×10^{-7}
1326.85	6.625×10^{-7}
1426.85	6.978×10^{-7}
1526.85	7.322×10^{-7}
1626.85	7.66×10^{-7}

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
1726.85	7.994×10^{-7}
1826.85	8.332×10^{-7}
1926.85	8.668×10^{-7}
2026.85	8.999×10^{-7}
2126.85	9.322×10^{-7}
2226.85	9.652×10^{-7}
2326.85	9.977×10^{-7}
2426.85	1.031×10^{-6}
2526.85	1.063×10^{-6}
2626.85	1.097×10^{-6}
2726.85	1.127×10^{-6}
2826.85	1.159×10^{-6}
2926.85	1.191×10^{-6}
2984.85	1.222×10^{-6}

Rhenium

- **Density** : 21 021 kgm^{-3}
- **Thermal Conductivity** :

Temperature [°C]	Thermal Conductivity [$Wm^{-1}C^{-1}$]
-253.15	39.6
226.85	49
726.85	52
1226.9	55
1726.9	62

- **Resistivity** :

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
20	1.9×10^{-7}
400	3×10^{-7}
800	6×10^{-7}
1200	7.5×10^{-7}
1600	9×10^{-7}
2200	1×10^{-6}

ThO₂

- **Density :** 10 000 *kgm⁻³*
- **Thermal Conductivity :**

Temperature [°C]	Thermal Conductivity [<i>Wm^{-1°C⁻¹}</i>]
26.85	14.7
126.85	11.1
326.85	7.38
526.85	5.54
726.85	4.44
826.85	4.03
926.85	3.7
1026.85	3.41
1126.85	3.17
1226.85	2.96
1326.85	2.77
1426.85	2.61
1526.85	2.47
1626.85	2.34
1726.85	2.22
1826.85	2.11
1926.85	2.02
2026.85	1.93
2126.85	1.85
2226.85	1.78
2326.85	1.71
2426.85	1.64

- **Resistivity :**

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [<i>Ωm</i>]
26.85	1.73×10^{-37}
126.85	1.71×10^{-26}
326.85	1.68×10^{-15}
526.85	5.28×10^{-9}
726.85	2.63×10^{-6}
826.85	1.66×10^{-5}

Temperature [°C]	Resistivity [Ωm]
926.85	16600
1026.85	2360
1126.85	444
1226.85	104
1326.85	29.4
1426.85	9.6
1526.85	3.55
1626.85	1.46
1726.85	0.656
1826.85	0.318
1926.85	0.165
2026.85	0.0903
2126.85	0.052
2226.85	0.0313
2326.85	0.0196
2426.85	0.0127
